

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF 3D COMPOSITE CONTINUOUS STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Many applications dealing with 3-D structures cannot be made of composites because the classical manufacturing processes do not give good results.

On the one hand, a 3-D composite structure can be made by assembling beams made by pultrusion. Mechanical joints between pultruded beams present efficiencies about 30 %. Thus, these structures must be reinforced in the critical areas and still they have weak points and very flexible joints. Because all of these disadvantages, pultruded beams are not recommended for 3-D structures.

On the other hand, classical filament winding can be used to make rectangular structures, but the cross-section is also rectangular, the ratio inertia/area being very low. Hence, generally speaking, 3-D composite structures made by filament winding will not take advantage of the low density of the material to generate light weight pieces.

A solution for designing and manufacturing 3-D composite structures is presented in this work. The 3-D final structure is made by assembling 2-D composite continuous frames.

Some prototypes of truck frames and buthane transportation structures will be presented. In order to avoid stress concentrations, all the frames are joined by adhesive and corners are stiff and strong enough owing to the fact that fibers are continuous.

KEYWORDS: 2D Structures; 3D Structures; Fibre Continuity.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the last three years, a new concept of 3-D continuous composite structure has been studied. A rectangular frame with T, L or C as cross-section will be the unit of the structure (Figures 1-3). By assembling these units, a 3-D continuous structure will be obtained (Figure 4). In this paper, the mechanical characterization of this new kind of structure will be carried out. Stiffness and strength parameters will be measured and substructures will be tested in order to get the mechanical behavior of corners and joints.

Finally, some real applications of this kind of structure will be shown: general structure of a transport mean (transport of butane bottles)(3D)...

2. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE LAMINATE

For the present work, the following laminate has been used:

Fiberglass E / vinylester DERAKANE resin

E_x	=	35.6	GPa
E_y	=	12.5	GPa
G_{xy}	=	4.14	GPa
ν_{xy}	=	0.22	
X	=	1060	MPa
X'	=	810	MPa
Y	=	145	MPa
Y'	=	180	MPa
S	=	72	MPa

A rectangular frame 1500 mm length and 500 mm width was used and the C-section had the following dimensions: 50 mm high, 25 mm width and 5 mm thickness.

In order to analyze the behavior of 2 and 3-D continuous composite structures, a theoretical and experimental study has been carried out. The present 2-D structure is composed of a continuous frame whose cross section is a C-section. The 3-D structure is made by assembling 2-D continuous frames.

The critical point of this study is double. First, the stiffness and strength of the beams that compose the frame and second, the stiffness and strength of the four corners. These two aspects can be analyzed properly by means of the 3 and 4P test bending (Figures 5 and 6). Since the profile is not symmetric with respect to the vertical axis, this load will generate a bending and torsion effect. This bending effect will let us know how the two longitudinal beams behave and the torsion effect will let us analyze the behavior of the four corners.

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The SARAH finite element code and the IDEAS postprocessor software has been used to obtain the stress distribution of the structure under the two types of load described in the last paragraph.

The finite element used here is based on the higher order shear theory and the penalty function theory (3). This scheme makes possible to analyze thin and thick plates, due to its general formulation. Some information about this finite element formulation and applications can be found in references (4-7)

In Figure 7, the stress distribution of the frame under a 3P test bending load is shown. A large area at the middle of the span of the longitudinal beams can be seen. There is also an area near the corners that show the torsion stress concentration.

In Figure 8, the stress distribution of the frame under a 4P test bending load is shown. A very large area at the middle of the span of the longitudinal beams can be seen. There is also an area near the corners that show the torsion stress concentration.

In both cases, the critical area is positioned on the middle of the span of the longitudinal beams.

4. TESTING OF 2 AND 3-D CONTINUOUS COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

3 and 4P bending tests have been carried out. The results of these tests are the following:

3P test bending results are shown in Figure 9. Displacement at the middle of the span (0.5 mm / mm) is represented in horizontal-axis. Total force (100 N / mm) is represented in vertical-axis. The area A of the graphic is linear, bending and torsion moments are present in this part. The area B is non-linear and plastic deformations are observed in the middle of the span of the longitudinal beam.

4P test bending results are shown in Figure 10. Displacement under the load point (0.5 mm / mm) is represented in horizontal-axis. Total force (100 N / mm) is represented in vertical-axis. The area A of the graphic is linear, bending and torsion moments are present in this part. In this case, the slope of the strain-stress line is higher than the 3P test bending as the linear beam theory predicts. The area B is non-linear and plastic deformations are observed in the middle of the span of the longitudinal beam.

Analyzing the results described in the last two paragraphs, it is possible to conclude that the behavior of the structure is excellent, the strength of the corner is very high and the weakest point under bending loads is positioned at the middle of the span.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a new concept of 2 and 3-D continuous composite structure is presented. A rectangular frame with T, L or C as cross-section is the unit of the structure . By assembling these units, a 3-D continuous structure is obtained.

The SARAH finite element code and the IDEAS pre and postprocessor software has been used to obtain the stress distribution of the structure under 3 and 4P bending loads.

3 and 4P bending tests have been carried out over 2-D structures and finally, a combined load has been applied to a 3-d continuous composite structures. In both cases, results are excellent.

6. REFERENCES

1. I. García, A. Miravete, J.J. Manso, Composites, n. 3, pp. 218-221, May, 1989.
2. I. García, J. J. Manso, A. Miravete, Ibérica Actualidad Tecnológica, nº 305, pp. 47-48, Jan 1989.
3. Miravete, A., Proc. 5th Conference Composite Structures, Vol 5, pp. 405-418, Paisley, Scotland, 1989.
4. Miravete, A, "The finite element Method applied to composites", Escribano, Zaragoza, Spain, 1987.
5. Miravete, A., Technical Report USAF WRDC-TR-89-4107
6. Miravete A., "Análisis del Comportamiento Resistente de Laminados de Poliester Reforzado y su Aplicación a los Medios de Transporte", Ph. D. University of Zaragoza, Spain, 1984.
7. Miravete A., Composites. Vol. 4, pp. 20, 1986.

FIGURE 1. 2-D Structure with T-section.

FIGURE 2. 2-D Structure with L-section.

FIGURE 3. 2-D Structure with C section.

FIGURE 4. Assembly of a 3-D structure.

FIGURE 5. 2-D Structure with C-section under a 3P bending load.

FIGURE 6. 2-D Structure with C-section under a 4P bending load.

Figure 7. Stress Distribution for a 3P test bending.

Figure 8. Stress Distribution for a 4P test bending.

Figure 9. Strain-Stress Diagram of a 3P test bending.

Figure 10. Strain-Stress Diagram of a 4P test bending.